

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF APPLYING PAPE-MASHE TECHNOLOGIES TO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE CREATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN.

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Abstract: This article highlights the didactic potential of pape-mashe technologies in shaping the creative development of children. It analyzes the mechanisms for developing imagination, thinking, aesthetic taste and motor skills of students through the integration of pape-mashe art into the educational process. It also substantiates with scientific and practical examples that the use of this technology increases independent thinking, diligence, and interest in artistic creativity in preschool children. The article also provides methodological recommendations for the effective use of pape-mashe technologies in the pedagogical process.

Key words: pape-mashe, children's creative development, didactic opportunities, art education, preschool education, aesthetic education, motor skills, creativity, applied arts, pedagogical technologies.

Introduction. The introduction of pape-mashe, technologies into the preschool educational process has a significant didactic impact on the creative development of children. Preschool educational organizations, in turn, serve as the main foundation for the formation of scientific and practical skills in children. The use of pape-mashe, technologies in the educational process serves to expand didactic opportunities, especially aimed at developing children's creative abilities. The main didactic opportunities of this technology are: Firstly, pape-mashe techniques teach children to work with a variety of materials, which develops their manual dexterity and imagination. Children demonstrate their creative abilities by creating various shapes and compositions using paper, glue, paints and other materials. This process helps children develop new ways of thinking, while at the same time strengthening their knowledge based on creative thinking by creating complex shapes from the simplest materials. Secondly, the didactic possibilities of pape-mashe, technologies develop imaginative and abstract thinking in children. By creating objects of various shapes, children master spatial concepts, geometric skills such as symmetry and proportion. As a result, they have the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practice during their learning process.

The use of pape-mashe technology in preschool education has a positive impact on the social and creative development of children. Through this activity, they acquire important skills such as working in a group, exchanging ideas, appreciating the opinions of others and clearly expressing their own opinion. Participation in collective work forms a culture of cooperation in children, which serves to increase their communicative potential. This technology also teaches children to make independent decisions, problem-solve, and try new approaches. The situations they encounter at each stage develop their ability to solve problems, direct their thoughts quickly and effectively, and achieve results. As a result, it stimulates the formation of the foundations of creative thinking and innovative thinking. Art classes play an important role in educating children's aesthetic taste, enhancing their perception of beauty and interest in creating new things. The didactic possibilities of pape-mashe technology are of great importance in this direction, expanding children's imagination by involving them in practical activities and strengthening their skills in working with images. The shapes and compositions created using pape-mashe materials activate children's imagination and serve as a solid foundation for the implementation of creative ideas. As a result, they not only learn to create something with their own hands, but also achieve significant progress in expressing their thoughts, experiencing beauty, and mastering practical knowledge.

Materials and methods. In the process of pape-mashe classes, it is necessary to adhere to a number of basic principles of didactics, including the principles of activity, linking theory and practice, demonstration, explanation, use of examples, didactic reproduction, scientificity, and application of knowledge. These principles play an important role in ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of the class. In particular, adherence to the demonstration principle is considered necessary for a thorough understanding of the materials and processes being studied during the classes.

The principle of demonstration. The application of the principle of demonstration in the educational process creates an opportunity for children to easily and clearly understand the material. Classes enriched with visual aids, in particular, increase children's interest in the subject or material and help them understand the content more deeply. The educational process becomes more lively and understandable through the use of videos, slides, photocopies and film materials, as well as artistic works created using pape-mashe technology, their copies. With the help of such tools, not only clear ideas about the subject are

formed, but also children develop their aesthetic taste and creative thinking. The sequence of classes, the organization from simple to complex, is important in increasing the effectiveness of education. The selection of new materials based on previous knowledge ensures the consistency and effectiveness of the learning process. Crafts based on pape-mashe technology and organized centers in this area, as well as excursions to museums of folk arts and crafts, broaden the aesthetic and moral outlook of children. Through such activities, children practically study the elements of art and crafts, which further develops their aesthetic vision and creative thinking potential. Pape-mashe works serve not as toys for children, but as objects of aesthetic and artistic value. This, in turn, contributes to a deeper understanding of art from a didactic point of view. Children strive to actively participate in lessons organized in the form of a game, which motivates them to master the educational material in an interesting and effective way.

Results. During the study, the following positive changes were observed in the creative development of children through the implementation of Pape-mashe technologies in the educational process:

Children's creative thinking and imagination were activated. They made new, different toys from ordinary paper; working with Pape-mashe technology developed children's fine motor skills. This helped them coordinate their hand movements and concentrate;

Through creative tasks given by the educator, children began to learn to make independent decisions and freely express their opinions. Children who actively participated in the activities developed an artistic and aesthetic taste, and their interest in art increased. The Pape-mashe technology had a positive effect on the formation of social skills among children, such as working together, listening to each other, and respecting each other.

Discussion. The book "Let's Learn Sculpture" by N. Beltyukova, S. Petrov and V. Kard describes how to teach pape-mashe classes to children effectively and in a playful way. It is considered appropriate to organize papier-mâché classes in a practical and playful way. As a result, children feel like active participants, which provides a high level of motivation in their learning process. Activities organized in the form of games help children learn the material in a more interesting and effective way. It allows children to strengthen their creative and practical skills, while at the same time increasing their interest and attention to the material being learned. Practical classes organized based on pape-mashe technology activate children, develop their creative potential, and

help them thoroughly and consistently master the knowledge they need to acquire in the educational process. Art coexists with humanity and is an integral part of it. Through works of art, a person understands and observes his inner world, his identity. Pape-mashe technologies serve as an important tool in shaping the spirituality and humanistic values of students. A person who loves art realizes his own capabilities and abilities through the works and great heritage of creative individuals. If we talk about the tasks of pape-mashe technology classes in preschool education, they can be divided into two main areas.

The first direction - this direction includes the main functions of papier-mâché technology in providing aesthetic and artistic education. It is aimed at fulfilling the following tasks:

- To teach children to see beauty in the environment and art, to understand it through the heart and mind, and to appreciate it with aesthetic taste;
- to instill a love of beauty in children through the pursuit of perfection and the formation of artistic perception;
- expand the scope of children's visual and artistic thinking, develop their ability to think figuratively;
- to stimulate imagination and fantasy, to reveal artistic and creative abilities; -teaching the elements of sculpture and construction art, developing initial skills;
- develop observation, visual memory, measuring and estimating skills, spatial imagination, figurative and logical thinking;
- to arouse interest in art, instill aesthetic values, and encourage appreciation of beauty.

The second direction - this direction reflects the expanded social, spiritual and pedagogical possibilities of pape-mashe technology. It covers the following tasks:

- To study the phenomena of nature and society through artistic means, to help understand existence;
- To strengthen the ideas of national pride and independence in the minds of young people;
- To develop moral qualities such as patriotism, humanity, and tolerance; -
- To educate discipline and patience in children through the formation of hard work and physical activity;
- To arouse interest in the profession, to provide initial practical skills for future work.

The use of pape-mashe technology in the preschool education system has a great impact on the learning process, as it helps children to acquire knowledge more deeply and qualitatively. This technology is considered one of the most effective methods in developing children's speech, increasing literacy, expressiveness, revitalizing the thinking process, and enhancing creative potential. The papier-mâché technique plays an important role not only in the construction, design and development of mathematics, science and nature, art centers, but also in the organization of literary and literacy classes. These classes help children develop aesthetic taste and increase their moral, work-related and ecological awareness. At the same time, it also plays an important role in preserving the rich spiritual and educational heritage of the Uzbek people. Teaching national art and culture, especially through applied arts and ancient technologies, helps to broaden the aesthetic and cultural outlook of children. Art circles organized in various regions of Uzbekistan, along with their unique cultural heritage, play a special role in teaching national culture. For example, architectural monuments in Bukhara and Samarkand, pottery in Rishton and Margilan, woodcarving in Khorezm, handicrafts in Shahrisabz and Khojaly, and traditional ceramic art in Gijduvan develop children's historical and aesthetic thinking. As a result, this, in turn, awakens in children a sense of respect and pride for national culture and forms thinking in harmony with global culture. The practical papier-mâché technologies of Madaripova Mukhtasarkhon Ravshanbekovna, who has been passing on the modern pape-mashe craft from generation to generation and developing it in new ways, help to further expand and develop the creative abilities of the younger generation. Her work in this field plays an important role not only in teaching children art, but also in forming creative thinking and aesthetic taste. Mukhtasarkhon Ravshanbekovna's methods introduce young people to traditional techniques and reveal their creative potential. These technologies also serve to increase students' interest in manual labor, the arts, and expand their horizons. As a result, modern pape-mashe technologies not only help preserve national heritage, but also strengthen children's respect for art, labor, and aesthetics.

Conclusion. The introduction of pape-mashe technologies into the educational process is an important factor in the creative development of children, in the formation of their aesthetic taste, in the development of independent thinking and practical skills. Through this technology, children expand their imagination in the process of creating various shapes and images, master a creative approach and can freely express their capabilities. The use of pape-mashe technology in

the educational process not only increases students' interest in art, but also helps them to deeply master the topics on a practical basis. This process also teaches them patience, accuracy, environmental culture, and teamwork skills. Therefore, the didactic possibilities of pape-mashe technology are one of the methods that should be widely used to enhance the creative potential of children, ensure their comprehensive formation as individuals, and increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

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